

9-THIOLPHENANTHRENE AND SOME OF ITS DERIVATIVES

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9-Thiolphenanthrene and some of its derivatives are described.

Except 3-thiolphenanthrene, prepared by Field (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 117, 1214), the other thiolphenanthrenes are not known. The author was inclined to prepare the 9-thiol compound in the expectation of preparing some thioindigoid dyes which would be of interest on the relation between colour and chemical constitution. Werner and his collaborators (*Annalen*, 1915, 321, 248) have shown that by the action of concentrated sulphuric acid on phenanthrene, three mono-sulphonic acids—2, 3, and 9 are produced, but a good method for their separation was not worked out. Fieser (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2460) later on has introduced a method by which these mono-sulphonic acids are obtained in better yield and in a more pure condition and incidentally he also discovered the presence of phenanthrene-1-sulphonic acid in these sulphonation products. 9-Thiolphenanthrene has been prepared from potassium-9-phenanthrene-sulphonate through sulphochloride and subsequent reduction, the potassium-9-phenanthrene-sulphonate having been prepared following Fieser's modified method (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

9-Thiolphenanthrene (I, R=H).

A mixture of potassium 9-phenanthrene-sulphonate (20 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (25 g.) was treated with phosphorus oxychloride (5 c.c.) and heated to 140° for 1 hour under reflux and then the oxychloride

distilled off. The semi-solid mass was then left in contact with ice-water for a long time. The yellowish white solid was next filtered and thoroughly washed with water. The sulphochloride, thus obtained, was mixed with zinc dust (80 g.) and to the mixture sulphuric acid (120 c.c. diluted with 360 c.c. of water), was gradually added. When the reaction had slackened the mixture was heated on water-bath for about 5 hours with frequent shaking. On cooling, the mixture was filtered and the residue collected. The thiolphenanthrene was then obtained from the residue by extraction with ether, drying the ethereal extract with fused calcium chloride and evaporation of ether. The thiol compound, thus obtained, was recrystallised from alcohol as white shining star-shaped crystals, m. p. 67° . It dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution with a light yellow colour but owing to oxidation the solution soon becomes turbid and the disulphide gradually separates out. (Found : S, 15.13. $C_{14}H_{10}S$ requires S, 15.24 per cent)

Phenanthrene-9-disulphide (II).—An alcoholic solution of iodine in slight excess was added to a solution of 9-thiolphenanthrene (0.5 g.) in 59 c.c. of alcohol, when yellowish white crystals at once separated out which were warmed for some time under reflux. On cooling, the crystals deposited were filtered and recrystallised from alcohol as light yellow sphere-shaped crystals, shrinking at 137° and melting at 149° . (Found : S, 15.26. $C_{20}H_{14}S_2$ requires S, 15.31 per cent).

9-Acetylthiolphenanthrene (I, R=COMe).—9-Thiolphenanthrene (2 g.) was heated on a water-bath under reflux with acetyl chloride (6 c. c.) for 2 hours when the almost colourless liquid gradually became much darker. The product was then poured into water, sodium hydroxide solution was added to it and the alkaline solution extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was then dried with fused calcium chloride and the ether distilled off. The residue left behind was then recrystallised from petroleum ether in white needles which shrink at 80° and melt at 93° . (Found : S, 12.4 : $C_{18}H_{12}OS$ requires S, 12.7 per cent).

9-Benzoylthiolphenanthrene, (I, R=COPh).—9-Thiolphenanthrene (2 g.) was heated with benzoyl chloride (6 c.c.) in an oil-bath at 150° - 160° for 3 hours. The dark product was poured into water and treated with sodium hydroxide solution till alkaline. The alkaline solution was then extracted with ether, the ethereal extract dried and the ether distilled off. The residue was recrystallised from benzene in yellowish-white clusters of needles, which shrink at 95° and melt at 109° . (Found : S, 9.85. $C_{21}H_{14}OS$ requires S, 10.19 per cent).

9-Methylthiophenanthrene (I, R=Me).—9-Thiophenanthrene (2 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (5 c.c., 20%) and to this solution dimethyl sulphate was added gradually. The oily substance separating was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract dried with calcium chloride and the ether distilled off. The oil left behind after the distillation of ether gradually solidified forming long needle-shaped crystals, m. p, 75°. (Found : S, 13.91. $C_{15}H_{12}S$ requires S, 14.28 per cent).

9-Phenanthrathiophene-2': 3'-dione (III).

(III)

9-Thiophenanthrene (5 g.) was treated with oxalyl chloride (12 g.) and the mixture left at ordinary temperature for 24 hours. The excess of oxalyl chloride was distilled off and the residue after the addition of carbon disulphide (20 c.c.) was treated slowly with powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.). The mixture was left at ordinary temperature for a short time and then refluxed for 1 hour. The carbon disulphide was then distilled off and the residue treated with crushed ice, filtered and washed. For purification, the residue was repeatedly extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution and the substance obtained as a red precipitate by acidifying the reddish yellow alkali solution with hydrochloric acid. The substance was further purified by recrystallising from acetic acid in fine red needles. It shrinks at 227° and melts at 245°. Provisionally the substance is represented by the above formula. (Found : C, 72.56; H, 3.12. $C_{11}H_8O_2S$ requires C, 72.72; H, 3.03 per cent).

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